

IMPORTANCE OF PERSPECTIVAL SYSTEM

By Edwin Amuga

Linear perspective utilizes mathematical principles to depict depth and space in art. Perspectives are used to represent how objects appear smaller as they move further into the distance. It serves to create a 3D-like impression as it adds depth and dimension to flat images. This was one of the developments during the Renaissance period that marked the rebirth of the European economic, cultural, political and artistic platforms after the middle ages especially in art, literature, and philosophy.

The perspectival system makes space organization appear uniform, harmonious, and proportional in design as it places the viewer on the central axis where they become the columns of the walls that support the element. In this way, the Brunelleschi's architecture the viewer and the objects within the larger spatial expanse a passive scaling system for the entirety of the church space.

The perspectival system in Brunelleschi's architecture makes it possible to mathematically calculate the scale of the objects within the pictures of the church making them appear more realistic as it aids in the measurement of spatial depth in a complex 3D-like imagination laid within the space. The columns exist above the height of entablature of the wall from the ground floor at one to two height ratio. The nave's lower adjacent spaces and the central axis of the San Lorenzo distance columns also exist in the same ration of one to two. The central axis upon which the viewer is placed is at the intersection of the uniformity of the spatial compositions. The viewer has the scaling system for the space entirety and objects in the space.

Bibliography

King, R. (2015). *Brunelleschi's dome: how a Renaissance genius reinvented architecture*.

Bloomsbury Publishing USA.